

Hedge Survey Notes

Date: enter date of survey

Hedgerow reference number: enter the hedge number which was assigned during step 1: mapping your hedgerow network.

Hedgerow characteristics

1. **Total hedge length (m):** measure the length of the whole hedgerow
2. **Hedge side surveyed:** state which side of the hedge was surveyed North (N), East (E), South (S) or West (W)
3. **Hedge growth stage:** write down the letter which best describes the whole hedgerow

a) Over trimmed, many gaps and sparse stems	b) Over trimmed, frequent healthy stems, requires height	c) Recently laid	d) Coppiced within the last 5 years
e) Planted within the last 5 years	f) Healthy dense hedge, frequent stems and over 2m in height	g) Over 3m and unmanaged for several years or on rotation	h) Over-mature gappy hedge
i) Hedge developed into a line of trees			

4. **Average height of hedge (m):** estimate the average height of the whole hedge to nearest 0.25m, excluding the bank or ditch
5. **Average width of hedge (m):** estimate the average width of the hedge to nearest 25cm at the widest point of the canopy, excluding the bank or ditch
6. **Average height of base of canopy (m):** estimate the distance from the ground to the base of the hedge canopy to nearest 25cm
7. **% of gaps:** estimate the % of gaps in the hedge to the nearest 5%
8. **Any gaps >5m in length:** Simply record 'Y' or 'N'
9. **Number of hedgerow trees:** for the whole hedgerow length count the number of trees distinct from the hedge itself. If the hedge is a line of trees with no distinct larger trees class the hedge as having no hedgerow trees.
10. **Number of hedgerow trees with veteran features:** count the number of hedgerow trees with any of the following features - dead branches; loose, split, missing and dead bark; tears, splits, scars, lightning strikes; hollow trunks or hollows in major limbs; or large areas of rot.
11. **Number of woody species**
12. **Three most dominant woody species:** List the three most dominant woody species within the hedge. Common species include, but are not restricted to:

Alder, common	Cherry, wild	Rowan	Hornbeam
Apple, crab	Chestnut, sweet	Spindle	Lime, large-leaved
Ash	Dogwood	Sycamore	Lime, small-leaved
Aspen	Elder	Wayfaring-tree	Maple, field
Beech	Elm, English	Willow, grey	Oak
Birch, downy	Elm, wych	Willow, goat	Pine, Scots
Birch, silver	Plum, wild	Hawthorn	Bramble
Blackthorn	Poplar, black	Hazel	Rose
Buckthorn	Privet, wild	Holly	

13. **Less than 10% cover of non-native woody species?:** Estimate whether there is less than 10% cover of non-native woody species. Record 'Y' or 'N'

Associated features

14. **Bank type:**

15. Bank height (m): to nearest 25cm

16. Ditch type:

Margins

17. Adjacent land use (you can select more than one land use type) : arable (a), pasture (b), cultivated (c), uncultivated (d), grazed (e), woodland (f), road (g), waterbody (h)

18. Margin width (m): estimate the distance from the edge of the hedgerow to the edge of any ploughed or otherwise cultivated or disturbed land.

19. Cover of nettles, cleavers and docks less than 20%?: Estimate whether the combined cover of nettles (*Urtica* spp.), cleavers (*Galium aparine*) and docks (*Rumex* spp.) within a 2m wide band alongside the hedgerow is less than 20% and simply record 'Y' or 'N'

Hedge management

20. Current management: flailed annually (a), flailed biannually (b), flailed every 3 to 5 years (c), side flailed only (d), coppiced within the last 5 years (e), recently laid (f), planted within last 5 years (g), no management (h)

Wildlife

21. Evidence of wildlife: Simply record 'Y' or 'N' and make a note of any evidence of wildlife using the hedge e.g. holes in the ground under or next to the hedge, chewed nut shells, bird nests, or animal tracks in the general notes section

General notes: Use this space to write any additional information that may affect the hedges management e.g. known presence of dormouse, screens road from house.